

FAMILY VALUES AND INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP CHARACTERISTICS OF WOMEN WHO HAVE EXPERIENCED DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

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Abstract. *This article empirically analyzes the socio-psychological causes of violence in Uzbek families. Using the methodology of the Russian psychologist A.N. Volkova "Determining roles in the family and the claim to marriage", the compatibility of family values of spouses is studied from the perspective of the woman and her husband. Our study focuses on the fact that the family roles of women subjected to domestic violence, family stability, interpersonal relationships, and family values of the husband and wife are the most important factors causing violence.*

Keywords: *family, physical and psychological violence, emotional-psychotherapeutic, external attractiveness, values and roles, national values.*

Introduction. In recent years, numerous scientific studies have been conducted by scholars around the world to examine the problem of domestic violence in family relationships, focusing on its gender, legal, and communicative aspects, as well as on developing effective ways to prevent such violence. However, despite these efforts, many unresolved issues remain in this field. Obtaining reliable data on this topic is often difficult, as family problems are usually kept private and not disclosed to outsiders. Most individuals experiencing domestic violence do not report it to the relevant authorities. This creates difficulties for researchers studying the problem, although considerable scientific research has been and continues to be carried out in Western countries and in Russia. The findings of these studies demonstrate that positive outcomes can only be achieved when comprehensive work is conducted with individuals who have suffered from domestic violence.

Main Part. We considered it important to study how domestic violence affects the value system of spouses and the indicators of interpersonal relationships within the family. The study examined the psychological characteristics of women's self-esteem and their relationships with others under the influence of physical, psychological, sexual, and economic violence. The imbalance and inconsistency in the value orientations of spouses inevitably lead to family conflicts, tensions, and acts of violence. When a husband fails to appreciate his wife's worth, ignores her interests and needs, and does not recognize her as an individual, the family atmosphere becomes unjustifiable and toxic.

In our research, to study the attitudes of women who have experienced domestic violence toward family values, we used the methodology of Russian psychologist A. N. Volkova titled "*Determining Family Roles and Marital Expectations.*" This questionnaire asks respondents—women who have suffered from violence—to assess the compatibility of family values from both their own and their husband's perspectives. Spouses' family values were assessed across several scales: sexual, personal compatibility of partners, domestic-household, educational, social activity, emotional-psychotherapeutic, and external attractiveness. Based on the mean scores obtained from

the application of this method, the degree of compatibility between the spouses' family values was determined.

Our findings revealed that in families affected by domestic violence, incompatibility between the husband's and wife's family values was one of the key factors leading to violence. Analysis of the family values of abused women showed discrepancies between the two partners' indicators, with significant mismatches in how each viewed their family values. According to the normative indicators of the method, these discrepancies clearly reflect the disbalance caused by violence. Specifically, the values related to sexual relations between spouses showed an index of **3.53**, indicating that under the influence of domestic violence, partners fail to recognize each other as sexual partners—this tendency was even more pronounced among victims of sexual violence.

Table 1.1

Indicators of Compatibility of Family Values Between Women Who Have Experienced Domestic Violence and Their Spouses (According to the Women's Assessment)

№	Values and Roles	Average arithmetic value (N=3.17)		The Degree of Compatibility of Spouses' Family Values
		A Woman's Attitude Toward Her Own Values	A Woman's Attitude Toward Her Husband's Values	
1.	Sexual Relations	6.72	3.19	3.53
2.	Spouses' Compatibility as Individuals	5.61	2.26	3.35
3.	Household and Domestic Sphere	7.37	2.67	3.70
4.	Parental and Educational Role	6.12	4.78	1.44
5.	Social Activity	4.56	5.01	-0.45
6.	Emotional and Psychotherapeutic Sphere	6.82	2.44	4.38
7.	Physical Attractiveness	5.29	1.33	3,96

In fact, to some extent, there may be satisfaction and contentment between spouses as sexual partners. However, the existence of violence against the woman makes it impossible for her to accept her husband emotionally and spiritually. At the same time, the compatibility index for the spouses' values regarding personal compatibility was 3.35. According to the methodology standards (values higher than 3 points indicate deviation from the norm), this index also differs from the normative value. The psychological interpretation of this empirical result can be expressed as follows: before the occurrence of violence, the spouses undoubtedly recognized each other as individuals to some degree. However, as the relationship deteriorated, disruptions in mutual recognition of each other as individuals emerged.

The compatibility of values concerning household management also showed a relatively high index of 3.70, which exceeds the normative threshold for differentiation between husband and wife’s values. In this regard, while the woman’s assessment of her own level of domestic management was within the normal range, her husband did not hold positive socio-psychological expectations toward her in managing household affairs.

Furthermore, the inconsistency in the spouses’ values was particularly pronounced in the emotional-psychotherapeutic dimension, with an index of 4.38, significantly above the norm. This value indicates the absence of warm and supportive relationships between the spouses—the husband does not show compliments, praise, kind words, or emotional support toward his wife. Naturally, this situation is especially emphasized in the evaluations of women who have experienced psychological violence. As for external attractiveness, there was also a noticeable deviation from the norm in the compatibility of values between spouses. This shows that men, to some extent, fail to accept their wives’ physical appearance. The lack of alignment in these values ultimately leads women to stop expecting sincere and genuine attitudes from their husbands.

However, two value dimensions were found to be free from discrepancies between the family values of husbands and wives. The first was parental (educational) roles, with an index of 1.44, and the second was social activity, with an index of –0.45—both below the normative value (3). This suggests that, despite domestic violence, many families remain together primarily for the sake of their children. In Uzbek culture, many women endure even the most intolerable behavior of their husbands for the well-being of their children. Similarly, there are also fathers who, despite being emotionally distant from their wives, show love and care toward their children. This explanation indicates that the continuation of marital life in such families is often due to parental roles. Conversely, in families without children, the marital bond is much more likely to break as a result of domestic violence.

In terms of **social activity roles**, compatibility between spouses can also be attributed to the wife’s respect and care for her husband’s parents or relatives, which in turn strengthens the perceived alignment in family values. The empirical analysis of compatibility in family values was further processed statistically according to traditional (nonparametric) comparative criteria used in such studies. The interpretation of these findings is presented below. The initial empirical values are related to the **family types of domestic violence victims** (see **Table 1.2**).

Table 1.2

Indicators of Family Values of Women Experiencing Domestic Violence (According to Family Type)

№	Criteria	Average color		U	p*
		Multi-layered family (n=167)	Nuclear family (n=150)		
1.	Sexual Relations	164.56	152.81	11596	0.248
2.	Spouses’ Compatibility as Individuals	162.36	155.26	11964	0.487
3.	Household and Domestic Sphere	158.81	159.21	12494	0.969
4.	Parental and Educational Function	159.56	158.38	12432	0.908
5.	Social Activity	154.97	163.49	11852	0.405

6.	Emotional and Psychotherapeutic Sphere	160.77	155.99	12073.5	0.639
7.	Physical Attractiveness	153.36	164.27	11582.5	0.285

Note: *No significant differences were observed between the indicators.*

According to the empirical data on the family values of women who have experienced domestic violence, no statistically significant differences were found between extended and nuclear families. The analysis of family values based on regional characteristics (see Table 3.3) revealed certain variations in women’s family values under the influence of violence. Empirical findings showed that women’s values regarding sexual relations, recognition of spouses as individuals, household management, social activity, and emotional-psychotherapeutic aspects were relatively similar. This similarity may indicate that women who have experienced domestic violence tend to form a common pattern of value orientations as members of the same social group.

However, differences were observed in the emotional-psychotherapeutic values of women aged 18–20 years. Despite being part of young families, their value orientations differed sharply from those of women in other age groups. Young married women expect affection, kind words, moral and emotional support, and appreciation from their partners, seeking psychological comfort in their marital relationships. Conversely, unexpected and inappropriate behavior associated with violence leads to changes in their value systems.

Conclusion. The positive and negative aspects of family values and interpersonal relationships among women who have experienced violence are an integral part of their socio-psychological profile. The findings of this study demonstrated that, although the family values of women subjected to violence share similar social characteristics, their attitudes—positive, negative, or indifferent—do not emerge spontaneously but are shaped by psychological and social factors. Therefore, it is essential to establish an effective psychological support system aimed at helping victims of violence overcome the psychological pressures they face. Otherwise, indifference toward women who experience domestic violence will inevitably lead to the deepening and worsening of this social problem. Hence, based on both the theoretical framework and empirical research presented in this study, it is crucial and necessary to develop a comprehensive psychological system for the prevention of domestic violence and the protection of women’s mental well-being.

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